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Public administration issues in the field of fire safety

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Abstract. Ensuring fire safety within the framework of public administration, like any other activity, has its own scientific basis. It includes various theories that study and investigate individual aspects of this activity, are in specific relationships, relationships and dependencies. Among them are the issues of organizing the fire department and managing its forces. The main content of organizational activity is the practical leadership of people - the coordination of joint actions and their regulation at all stages of the management process. From the standpoint of the process approach, organizational activity is viewed not as a one-time action, but as a series of continuous interrelated actions, that is, a process. And from the point of view of the above approaches, management is, first of all, the art of a leader to understand the situation, reveal its features and choose the optimal solution from a variety of possible ones, and then follow scientific recommendations in the field of management, which are general and universal in nature. Therefore, the fire safety system will be considered from a managerial position - as the organization of its activities to ensure fire safety and from organizational and structural - as a structure designed to implement organizational decisions in the field of fire safety.

Introduction

The relevance of the topic of the article is determined, first of all, by the fact that at the present stage of development of scientific and technological progress, issues of comprehensive, including management, fire safety in the modern world play an increasingly important role. Fires, as one of the most destructive phenomena, entail human casualties, significant and sometimes irreparable damage to the natural environment and human civilization, its material and spiritual values.

The systematic approach involves considering various processes and phenomena in management as a system. At the same time, it is customary to understand a control system as an isolated integral set of interconnected functional elements, which has new qualities in relation to its constituent elements. Integrity means that in relation to the environment, the system appears and, accordingly, is perceived as something single. In this case, all elements of the system or some of them can, in turn, be a structure-forming part of any subsystem. Currently, the systematic approach is considered a universal research methodology. It is widely used in modern theory and practice of organization management. At the same time, the analysis of research experience shows that the use of only one approach in its classical

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form for the purposes of systemic research, most often not only does not give a significant effect, but is often harmful. Hence the need for an integrative balanced use of various methodological approaches in relation to each specific study of systems (organizations). Therefore, the systematic approach is legitimately interpreted as a system of approaches.

Since modern organizations are open systems, they receive energy, information, material and other resources from the external environment to support their activities. At the same time, each organization gives the products of its activities to the external environment. Thus, the product of the activity of the fire safety system can be considered the maintenance of constant readiness to eliminate emergency situations associated with fires.

Theory of the matter

Fires and all processes related to their occurrence and development require purposeful management, which provides, along with the implementation of organizational, technical and economic measures, increasing the role of legal regulation and coordination of relations between relevant government agencies, businesses and other bodies, which should provide fire protection of settlements and facilities, as well as further improvement of their activities and interaction. Given that fire safety is one of the most important types of public safety, as well as the exceptional importance of fire safety in the protection of human life, national wealth and the environment, the issues of mechanisms of state management of fire safety are reflected in the works of Ukrainian and foreign scientists.

The analysis of modern literature sources of specialists and researchers indicates specific gaps in the conduct of research related to the scientific and theoretical justification of the mechanisms of public administration in the field.

Discussion of results

Questions about the implementation by public authorities of various areas of fire safety have been the object of close attention of legal scholars. Despite this, the scientific literature has not yet developed a generally accepted concept of social relations arising in the activities of public authorities and society to establish and practically implement an effective state legal system necessary to ensure a sufficient level of fire safety. The emerging new threats to society from fires make us constantly search for new, more modern ways and means of preventing fires, successfully extinguishing them and minimizing harmful consequences. One of these ways can be considered the conduct of scientific and legal research in the field of regulation of public relations that develop while ensuring fire safety.

Fire safety is an integral element of national security, which includes the activities of the state and society to create and ensure a stable state of excluding conditions and causes that can cause an emergency in the form of uncontrolled combustion, and in the event of the latter, ensures the earliest possible termination of its spread and minimization of damage to it. primary and secondary damaging factors to the interests of the individual, society and the state, material values and the environment.

The fire safety system is based on the social interaction of subjects and objects of fire safety, the main purpose of which is to organize and maintain a dynamically constant fire safety state of territories, enterprises, institutions, technological equipment and settlements.

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The goals and objectives assigned to the fire safety system are achieved through the implementation by its subjects of the functions assigned to them, through the powers of technical, legal and social methods of influence, interconnected and applied in various combinations, based on the characteristics of fire safety facilities ...

A fire regime is a procedure for regulating public relations established and ensured by the norms of various branches of law, which determines the conditions for the normal functioning of the elements of the fire safety system, in order to create and maintain the necessary and sufficient level of fire safety of the relevant objects.

A legal entity should be held administratively liable for misconduct in the field of fire safety, if it does not prove that, with the degree of care and discretion required from it by the current regulatory legal acts, it took all measures to properly comply with the requirements of the law. In this case, a legal entity is released from administrative responsibility if it proves that the improper fulfillment of the requirements of regulatory legal acts was due to force majeure, that is, extraordinary and unavoidable circumstances under these conditions. The legislator should clearly indicate which particular circumstances are extraordinary and insurmountable. For example, natural and man-made emergencies, environmental emergencies, interethnic, interfaith and regional conflicts accompanied by violent actions.

Analyzing the reforms in public fire safety on the example of the United States, it should be noted that the reform of this system took place almost a century ago and has come a long way and has been repeatedly criticized. In particular, the 32nd President of the United States - F.D. Roosevelt. In his opinion - the state in the process of its governing bodies should stop playing the role of "night watchman" and come out of the shadows. The state must not only point the way with restrictive "road signs", which must be followed by all its subjects and objects, but to lead this way, set the direction and speed of movement to build a truly democratic state with the rule of law and social justice. " It should be noted that when the state begins to withdraw obligations without creating effective mechanisms for their replacement, then before the lack of clear safety requirements, leveled and a lot of work done by a large number of fire and rescue units and their employees, and the unstoppable force of such a powerful and unexplored to the end of the element as a fire, begins to get up, and cause irreparable significant damage. Analysis of the system of public administration, which was carried out almost 85 years ago, the theorist and pragmatist of public administration F.D. Roosevelt (whose activities coincided with the Great Depression in the United States and World War II) proposed his political program in the "New Deal (1933-1938)" and is relevant to today's government in the field of fire safety in Ukraine. Insurance companies that insure the so-called "fire risks", due to the legal traditions of Ukraine at this stage can not transparently ensure the declaration and establishment of norms and standards of fire safety, as is the case in the United States. In addition, there are very high corruption risks, as insurance companies pursue their own commercial interests, as noted by Yu.F. Brigham and M.S. Erhardt - "the dollar received today,..., is more valuable than the dollar that will be received in the future, because if you already have it, you can reinvest it in business, get interest and in the future get more than one dollar. " Thus, analyzing the consequences of the Thomas fire in the United States (December 2017 - March 2018, Ventura and Santa Cruz counties, California), based on statistics on the number of cells, fire, area of its distribution, the number of destroyed houses, buildings, structures, and using the statistical calculation methods underlying the risk-based approach, it can be demonstrated that the risk of fire, risk of destruction, risk of destruction of

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buildings, or risk of death in fires in the last 5 years for Ventura counties and Santa Cruz, California, has grown rapidly. Therefore, the insurance premium paid for fire risk insurance should usually increase proportionally, ie this will increase the initial income of the insurance company in a certain short period of time, which in financial management is called "cash flow at the moment", because people are scared of this event now and here, and do not want to be left with anything in the future.

There are several aspects of management activities in the management of fire fighting forces, where in modern conditions the introduction of management technologies is extremely important. First of all, these are the processes of forecasting, programming, assessing and tracking changes in the states of the operational fire situation. You cannot manage if there is no initial data for this. It is also necessary to have timely, reliable and complete information about everything that happens within the territory of responsibility. The technology of activities in this direction includes: the establishment of general, unified indicators of fire risks, adequately characterizing the state of protected areas and objects; ensuring proper consistency, logic in the systematization of such indicators so that they generally give a real picture of the fire situation (both current and in development); creation of organizational and technical conditions for the prompt and accurate transmission of the necessary information through all structural subsystems, links and their units involved in these processes; application of identical methods, procedures and operations of analysis and characteristics of the studied and programmed objects; the use of identical forms of recording information materials and other points inherent in the considered aspect of the management of fire protection forces.

The use of management technologies in the practice of programming and planning the integrated development of the fire safety system of the territory and the structure of the fire safety forces is relevant. Without such technologies, in the conditions of significant independence of various control bodies at the territorial and municipal levels, control bodies of fire protection forces of various departmental affiliations and forms of ownership, the concentration of the main financial, economic and material resources mainly in the hands of entrepreneurial structures, the inclusion of many managed objects in the solution of the corresponding problems, nothing serious can be done. We need uniform terms and methods for the development of proposed activities in the formations, organizations and institutions of the fire protection forces, identical forms and indicators of program and planning documents, an interconnected, agreed procedure for passing and approving programs and plans, acceptable procedures for considering controversial issues, certain mechanisms of mutual control, etc. e. Modern social practice testifies to the development of targeted programs developed and implemented at various levels - from national to local. It also requires adequate management technologies capable of imparting proper organization, the necessary regulation and efficiency to activities in this direction. Within the framework of the entire fire safety system, a lot of management decisions are made and are acting, both current, operational and prospective, regulatory and strategic. Almost all officials have to constantly justify various options for solutions, look for alternatives to resource provision and temporary implementation, coordinate various decisions (and their provisions) among themselves, actively analyze the progress of implementation of some decisions and take into account its results when preparing others, summarize the results of implementation, decisions and remove them from control, deal with other issues in this voluminous and responsible area of management. Here we need scientifically based technologies for the preparation, adoption and implementation of managerial decisions, starting with a

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unified language and ending with graphic forms of specific documents. Everything should be clear, clear, consistent and understandable for both decision-makers and performers. A weak point in the management of fire fighting forces remains control technologies associated with continuous monitoring of controlled processes, their study, measurement and comparison, their objective correlation with management models expressed in decisions, their norms and requirements.

In this aspect, feedback technologies are of great interest, providing a reliable reflection of the results of control actions. The technologies of organizational forms of management activity are equally significant, because their effectiveness is determined by several conditions: administrative and legal conditions associated with the competence of the corresponding event (what are its capabilities), organizational and functional, expressed in the nature of its preparation and the procedure for conducting (is it ready and whether its capabilities were used), socio-psychological (the participants' interest in this event), physiological (the participants' well-being, their ability to issue and assimilate information), technical (provision of means of recording and fixing information), etc. All this should be summarized in one system - organizational technology, in particular, allowing to obtain the desired intellectual management product. Management technologies are a whole area of theoretical searches and practical experiments. Their promotion to the agenda is due to the objective complication and rise in the cost of management processes in all state spheres, including in the field of fire safety, and at the same time the strengthening of their role (significance) in all spheres of society.

Conclusion

Today and in the foreseeable future, it is impossible to streamline the management activities and, in general, the fire brigade control system without the development and mastering of management technologies for all the most important aspects of the organization and functioning of the fire brigade. Moreover, this is not about giving new names to old bureaucratic procedures and operations, not about simply filling the workplaces of the personnel of the management body with modern electronic means, but about a qualitatively new understanding and reform of the defining manifestations of management in the field of ensuring the country's fire safety. Administrative technologies, if they really take place, should cause profound transformations in everything related to this systemic social phenomenon. Knowledge and possession of the methodological foundations for assessing the effectiveness of state fire safety management can help in this.

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